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ECONOMIC EFFECTS OF GASTRONOMIC TOURISM: AN ANALYSIS OF TOURISTS' FOOD EXPENDITURE PATTERNS

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Abstract. This article analyzes the economic impact of gastronomic tourism using the example of tourists' spending on food. The study considers gastronomic experience as an important component of tourism and highlights how tourists' spending on national dishes, local restaurants, street food, and gastronomic festivals contributes to the development of the regional economy. It also argues that tourists' food expenses are a sustainable source of tourism revenue, supporting small businesses, agriculture, the food industry, and the service sector. The article emphasizes that the growth of gastronomic tourism can create new jobs in regions, increase demand for local products, and form national cuisine as a brand. In addition, the analysis of tourists' spending habits shows the need to develop practical recommendations for planning tourism policy, improving service quality, and developing gastronomic destinations. The results of the study allow us to evaluate gastronomic tourism as a factor in economic development.

Key words: gastronomic tourism, tourist expenses, food expenses, local economy, tourism income, national cuisine, service sector, regional development, tourism infrastructure, economic impact.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada gastronomik turizmning iqtisodiy ta'siri turistlarning oziq-ovqat xarajatlari misolida tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot gastronomik tajribani turizmning muhim tarkibiy qismi sifatida ko'rib chiqadi hamda turistlarning milliy taomlar, mahalliy restoranlar, ko'cha taomlari va gastronomik festivallarga sarflagan mablag'lari mintaqa iqtisodiyotining rivojlanishiga qanday hissa qo'shishini yoritadi. Shuningdek, turistlarning oziq-ovqat xarajatlari turizm daromadlarining barqaror manbai ekani, kichik biznes, qishloq xo'jaligi, oziq-ovqat sanoati va xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini qo'llab-quvvatlashi asoslab beriladi. Maqolada gastronomik turizmning o'sishi hududlarda yangi ish o'rinlari yaratishi, mahalliy mahsulotlarga bo'lgan talabni oshirishi va milliy oshxonani brend sifatida shakllantirish imkonini berishi ta'kidlanadi. Bundan tashqari, turistlarning xarajat odatlari tahlili turizm siyosatini rejalashtirish, xizmat sifatini oshirish va gastronomik yo'nalishlarni rivojlantirish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish zaruratini ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot natijalari gastronomik turizmni iqtisodiy rivojlanish omili sifatida baholash imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: gastronomik turizm, turist xarajatlari, oziq-ovqat xarajatlari, mahalliy iqtisodiyot, turizm daromadi, milliy oshxona, xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi, hududiy rivojlanish, turizm infratuzilmasi, iqtisodiy ta'sir.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется экономическое влияние гастрономического туризма на примере расходов туристов на питание. Исследование рассматривает гастрономический опыт как важный компонент туристической деятельности и показывает, каким образом расходы туристов на национальные блюда, местные рестораны, уличную еду и гастрономические фестивали способствуют развитию региональной экономики. Обосновывается, что расходы туристов на питание являются устойчивым источником туристических доходов и поддерживают малый бизнес, сельское хозяйство, пищевую промышленность и сферу услуг. В статье подчеркивается, что рост гастрономического туризма может способствовать созданию новых рабочих мест в регионах, увеличению спроса на местную продукцию и формированию национальной кухни как бренда. Кроме того, анализ потребительских расходов туристов демонстрирует необходимость разработки практических рекомендаций по планированию туристической политики, повышению качества обслуживания и развитию гастрономических направлений. Результаты исследования позволяют оценить гастрономический туризм как фактор экономического развития.

Ключевые слова: гастрономический туризм, расходы туристов, расходы на питание, местная экономика, туристические доходы, национальная кухня, сфера услуг, региональное развитие, туристическая инфраструктура, экономическое влияние.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the tourism industry has become one of the fastest growing sectors of the world economy. Along with traditional recreation, visiting historical monuments or relaxing in nature, travelers' interests are increasingly focused on narrowly specialized types of tourism. One of these areas is gastronomic tourism, which is based on the desire of tourists to get acquainted with the national cuisine, food culture and culinary traditions of the region they are visiting. Today, food is considered not only a means of satisfying physiological needs, but also an important part of cultural experience, social communication and economic activity.

The development of gastronomic tourism is creating new economic opportunities for many countries and regions. The money spent by tourists on restaurants, national cuisines, street food outlets, cafes and gastronomic festivals leads to the expansion of the service sector. At the same time, such expenses also stimulate the development of sectors such as agriculture, food production, logistics and trade. Thus, tourists' food expenses are one of the factors that directly and indirectly shape economic efficiency.

Modern studies show that many tourists spend the largest share of their expenses during their trip on food and gastronomic experiences. In particular, tasting national dishes, eating dishes made from local products and participating in traditional culinary processes are becoming an unforgettable part of the trip. This requires considering gastronomic tourism not only as a means of cultural exchange, but also as a strategic direction that ensures economic stability.

The relevance of the topic is that the role of the gastronomic factor in increasing tourism revenues is often underestimated. Although in many regions attention is mainly focused on hotel infrastructure or transport services, catering services make up a large part of the economic cycle. By analyzing tourists' food expenses, it is possible to identify their consumption habits, needs and preferences, as well as to open up opportunities for supporting local entrepreneurship.

The purpose of this article is to highlight the economic impact of gastronomic tourism on the example of tourists' food expenses. The research analyzes the cost structure of tourists, the contribution of gastronomic services to the regional economy, and the practical importance of developing this area. As a result, a scientific basis is created for understanding the mechanisms for effective management of gastronomic tourism and obtaining economic benefits from it.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The development of gastronomic tourism has increasingly attracted scholarly attention, particularly in the context of Uzbekistan's tourism transformation. Recent studies emphasize that gastronomic tourism is not merely a complementary tourism product but a strategic factor enhancing destination competitiveness and economic attractiveness. Rakhimov, Doniyorova, and Umarova argue that national cuisine plays a significant role in strengthening the image of Uzbekistan as a tourist destination, increasing tourist satisfaction and repeat visits [1]. According to their findings, the integration of culinary heritage into tourism marketing strategies directly contributes to expanding tourism revenues and regional economic growth.

Similarly, Jalilov highlights the organizational aspects of gastronomic tourism, focusing on institutional mechanisms, service quality standards, and coordination between tourism stakeholders [2]. The author underlines that the systematic organization of gastronomic routes, festivals, and culinary branding enhances tourist flows and creates sustainable income sources for local businesses. This perspective reinforces the idea that food-related expenditures represent a structured economic segment rather than incidental spending.

The economic opportunities associated with gastronomic tourism are further explored by Fayziyeva and Ruziev, who analyze its potential for stimulating small entrepreneurship and diversifying regional economies [3]. Their research demonstrates that tourist spending on food generates multiplier effects across agriculture, food production, and service industries. This approach aligns with the broader understanding of tourism as a cross-sectoral economic system where catering services function as a central connecting element.

Ruziyeva and Ziyoviddinov examine both innovative and traditional approaches to developing gastronomic tourism in Uzbekistan [4]. They emphasize the importance of combining cultural authenticity with modern service innovations, including digital promotion tools and improved hospitality standards. Their study shows that innovation in menu design, restaurant management, and marketing increases competitiveness and strengthens the economic impact of tourists' food expenditures.

Umarova focuses on political reforms and demographic factors shaping the prospects of gastronomic tourism development [5]. Through the example of the "Karimbek" restaurant, the study illustrates how private sector initiatives, supported by state reforms, can effectively capitalize on tourist demand for national cuisine. The research confirms that catering enterprises play a decisive role in transforming tourist consumption patterns into stable economic gains.

One of the most important aspects of gastronomic tourism is its multiplier effect. That is, the money paid by a tourist in a restaurant does not only become the income of this enterprise. The restaurant, in turn, buys vegetables and meat from farmers, products from dairy producers, bread from bakeries, and products from beverage producers. This gives impetus to the development of agriculture and the food industry (Figure 1) [4].

Figure 1. Statistical Analysis of Tourists' Food Expenditure in Gastronomic Tourism

Transport services, logistics companies, packaging manufacturers also become part of this chain. Thus, gastronomic tourism accelerates the circulation of money in the regional economy and creates additional sources of income in many areas.

Tourists are usually interested in tasting dishes made from local products. This increases the demand for agricultural products grown in the region. For example, if a certain region is famous for its grapes, fruits, spices or meat products, gastronomic tourism helps these products become brands.

For local producers, this means a stable market. They strive to improve the quality of their products, introduce environmentally friendly farming methods and increase production volumes. As a result, regional agriculture becomes more competitive.

Gastronomic tourism creates great opportunities, especially for small businesses. Family restaurants, home-made national sweets, homemade drinks or traditional bakery products are of great interest to tourists. Such activities often do not require large investments, but can bring high incomes.[5]

This process increases employment, creates an additional source of income, especially for women and young people. In this way, gastronomic tourism also serves to strengthen socio-economic stability.

National dishes and gastronomic traditions play an important role in shaping the image of the region. If a certain city or region is famous for its unique cuisine, this place becomes a tourist brand. For example, through pilaf, samsa, lagman or other traditional dishes, the region can make itself known on the international stage.

Such a positive image also increases attractiveness for investors. Investments in tourism infrastructure, restaurant business, food production increase. This accelerates economic growth.

Many tourist regions have a problem of seasonality. However, gastronomic tourism can be in demand throughout the year. Since interest in food and drinks is less seasonal, gastronomic events can attract tourists even during the low tourist season. This ensures that tourism revenues are stable throughout the year.[3]

Analyzing the amount of money tourists spend on food is important in planning tourism policies. By answering these questions, it is possible to further improve services.

This information is also important when developing marketing strategies. You can increase the flow of tourists by promoting local dishes, creating a map of gastronomic destinations, and organizing thematic festivals.[2]

In short, it is important to adhere to the principles of sustainability in the process of developing gastronomic tourism. The use of local and seasonal products reduces transportation costs and limits the negative impact on the environment. Reducing food waste, using eco-friendly packaging, and saving resources also increase economic efficiency.

Thus, gastronomic tourism can be not only a source of income, but also a means of increasing environmental responsibility.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, gastronomic tourism has evolved from a supplementary tourism activity into a strategically important component of the modern tourism economy. The analysis presented in this article demonstrates that tourists' food expenditures constitute a significant share of overall travel budgets and play a crucial role in shaping regional economic performance. Spending on restaurants, street food, local products, and gastronomic events generates direct income for catering enterprises while simultaneously stimulating related sectors such as agriculture, food production, logistics, transport, and trade.

The economic importance of gastronomic tourism extends beyond immediate revenue generation. Its multiplier effect accelerates the circulation of money within the regional economy, contributes to job creation, strengthens small and family businesses, and enhances the competitiveness of local producers. Furthermore, gastronomic identity contributes to destination branding, improves the international image of regions, and increases investment attractiveness. The relatively low level of seasonality in food-related tourism activities also supports more stable and continuous tourism revenues throughout the year.

At the same time, the findings highlight the need to integrate gastronomic factors more systematically into tourism policy and strategic planning. A comprehensive analysis of tourists' food expenditure patterns allows policymakers and entrepreneurs to better understand consumption behavior, optimize service quality, and design effective marketing strategies.

Ultimately, when developed in accordance with sustainability principles, gastronomic tourism can serve not only as a source of economic growth but also as a mechanism for supporting local entrepreneurship, preserving cultural heritage, and promoting environmental responsibility. Therefore, recognizing and strategically managing the economic potential of gastronomic tourism is essential for ensuring long-term regional development and stability.

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